

IMPROVEMENT AND SUPPORT OF PHYSICS COMPETENCIES OF GENERAL EDUCATION SCHOOL STUDENTS

S.A. Tursinbaev

*¹Nukus State Pedagogical Institute named after Ajiniyoz,
Doctor of Philosophy (Ph.D.) in Physical and Mathematical Sciences.*

E-mail: sabirbay_fizika@mail.ru

Annotation. *This article examines the issues of developing and supporting students' competencies in physics in general education schools. The methodology of teaching physics has been improved based on modern educational requirements, and data obtained from practical experiments have been analyzed. During the research, the effectiveness of traditional and innovative pedagogical methods was studied, and practical recommendations were developed to increase students' interest in physics and develop scientific competencies. The advantages of the competency-based approach, ways to modernize the educational process, and issues of using modern technologies in teaching physics are highlighted.*

Key words: *physics teaching methodology, competency-based approach, student competencies, modern educational technologies, pedagogical innovations, STEM education, interactive learning, practical skills.*

Introduction

In the modern education system, educational strategies based on a competency-based approach are gaining significant importance. The main idea of this approach is not only to provide students with theoretical knowledge but also to develop practical skills, analytical thinking abilities, and the ability to apply knowledge in real-life situations. Particularly in teaching physics, the competency-based approach plays an important role in shaping students' scientific worldview, understanding natural phenomena, and developing skills to solve technical problems.

Globally, there is a trend towards transitioning to a competency-based approach in education systems. According to international assessment programs such as PISA and TIMSS, East Asian countries (Singapore, South Korea, Japan) and countries like Finland demonstrate high performance in students' natural sciences, including physics. The experience of these countries shows that giving ample space to practical classes, laboratory work, and project activities in physics teaching significantly increases students' scientific competencies [1].

In the Uzbekistan education system, competency-based curricula and standards have been developed in recent years. However, there are several problems in the

practice of teaching physics in general education schools: the theoretical nature of educational materials, lack of laboratory equipment, insufficient skills of teachers in using innovative methods, and declining student interest in physics.

The purpose of this research is to improve the methodology for effectively forming and developing student competencies in physics in general education schools and to develop practical recommendations. Within the framework of the research, the following tasks were defined:

1. Study the theoretical foundations of the competency-based approach in physics teaching;
2. Determine the status of forming physics competencies among general education school students;
3. Develop innovative methods and tools for developing student competencies in physics teaching;
4. Experimentally test the effectiveness of the proposed methodology and develop practical recommendations.

The relevance of the research lies in the fact that forming students' fundamental knowledge and skills in physics is important not only for academic success but also for preparing specialists who meet the requirements of future professional activities and innovative economy [2].

Methods

To achieve the research goal, a complex of theoretical and empirical methods was used. Analysis of scientific literature allowed for studying the theoretical foundations of the competency-based approach, summarizing foreign experience, and identifying trends in modern physics teaching methodology [3].

The following methods were used during the research:

1. Theoretical methods: analysis of scientific-pedagogical literature; study and comparison of foreign and local experiences; pedagogical modeling; analysis and synthesis.

2. Empirical methods:

- Pedagogical observation
- Questionnaires and testing
- Pedagogical experiment
- Mathematical-statistical analysis

The research was conducted at Secondary School No. 27 in Nukus from 2023 to 2024. The experimental work involved 8th and 9th-grade students, with a total of 96 students participating. Additionally, 4 physics teachers were involved in the research. The pedagogical experiment was conducted in three stages:

1. Diagnostic stage (September-December 2023) – determining the level of students' competencies in physics, studying existing problems.

2. Formative stage (January 2024 – December 2024) – implementing the developed methodology in the educational process, organizing special courses for teachers.

3. Final stage (January 2025) – analyzing the obtained results, evaluating effectiveness, drawing conclusions, and developing recommendations.

Within the framework of the research, the following types of student competencies in physics were identified and evaluated:

1. Scientific-theoretical competencies (understanding physical concepts, laws, and theories) [4].

2. Practical-experimental competencies (conducting experiments, performing measurements, processing results) [6-5].

3. Problem-solving creative competencies (solving physics problems, scientific research skills) [7-8].

4. Information-communicative competencies (searching for information, processing, presenting) [9-10].

5. Social-personal competencies (working collaboratively, self-assessment) [11-12].

Special diagnostic tools were developed to assess students' competency levels: tests, problems, laboratory works, and project assignments.

Results

According to the results of surveys and tests conducted during the diagnostic stage, students' competencies in physics were distributed as follows (Table 1):

Table 1. Level of students' physics competencies at the diagnostic stage

Competency Types	High Level (%)	Medium Level (%)	Low Level (%)
Scientific-theoretical	18.5	42.3	39.2
Practical-experimental	12.7	37.8	49.5
Problem-solving creative	9.2	31.5	59.3
Information-communicative	22.4	45.1	32.5
Social-personal	25.6	48.2	26.2

As can be seen from the table, students' practical-experimental and problem-solving creative competencies are relatively low. This indicates insufficient attention to practical exercises, laboratory work, and problem-solving situations in physics teaching.

According to the survey results among teachers, the following main difficulties were identified in implementing the competency-based approach in physics teaching (Table 2):

Table 2. Difficulties in implementing the competency-based approach in physics teaching

Difficulties	Percentage of Teachers (%)
Lack of laboratory equipment	78.4
Insufficient knowledge of competency-based approach methodology	65.3
Excessive curriculum load	62.5
Insufficient skills in using modern pedagogical technologies	58.2
Unclear criteria for assessing competencies	52.7

During the formative stage, the following methodology was developed and implemented to develop students' competencies in physics:

1. **“Observing and Investigating Physical Phenomena” module** – to develop students' skills in observation, conducting experiments, and analyzing results.
2. **“Physics Problem Workshop” module** – to develop problem-solving creative competencies through solving problems of various difficulty levels.
3. **“Physics and Modern Technologies” module** – to study practical applications of physics laws, creating models and mockups.
4. **“Physical Research Projects” module** – to form students' scientific research skills.
5. **“Virtual Physics Laboratory” module** – to model physical processes using modern information and communication technologies.

Each module was provided with educational-methodical materials, practical tasks, and assessment criteria. During the formative stage, special seminars and training sessions were organized for teachers, and recommendations on using innovative methods were provided.

At the end of the research, the results obtained at the diagnostic and final stages were compared (Table 3):

Table 3. Level of students' competencies at the beginning and end of the experiment

Competency Types	Beginning of Experiment			End of Experiment		
	High (%)	Middle (%)	Low (%)	High (%)	Middle (%)	Low (%)
Scientific-theoretical	18.5	42.3	39.2	32.7	48.5	18.8
Practical-experimental	12.7	37.8	49.5	29.8	52.3	17.9
Problem-solving creative	9.2	31.5	59.3	24.5	45.7	29.8
Information-communicative	22.4	45.1	32.5	38.2	49.6	12.2
Social-personal	25.6	48.2	26.2	41.3	47.8	10.9

As can be seen from the results, the proposed methodology helped to increase students' levels of all types of competencies. Particularly significant growth was observed in practical-experimental competencies (the number of students at a high level increased from 12.7% to 29.8%).

Discussion of Results

The research results show that for effective implementation of the competency-based approach in physics teaching, it is necessary to combine traditional educational methods with innovative technologies, strengthen the connection between theory and practice, and stimulate students' active cognitive activity.

The proposed “Observing and Investigating Physical Phenomena” and “Physics and Modern Technologies” modules significantly increased students' practical-experimental competencies. These results are consistent with the conclusions of scientists [13-14] working in this field, which emphasize that teaching methods based on practical research are effective in increasing students' scientific understanding.

The “Physics Problem Workshop” and “Physical Research Projects” modules helped develop students' problem-solving creative competencies. In the process of solving physics problems, students not only gain a deeper understanding of the subject but also develop analytical thinking and problem-solving skills [15-16].

Through the “Virtual Physics Laboratory” module, students' information-communicative competencies increased.

Group projects, collaborative research, and peer assessment methods positively influenced the development of social-personal competencies.

According to the research results, the following conditions are important for effective implementation of the competency-based approach in physics teaching:

1. Modernizing the curriculum, optimizing the volume of theoretical material, and increasing the share of practical activities;
2. Expanding opportunities to use modern laboratory equipment and digital educational resources;
3. Enhancing teachers' professional competencies, equipping them with innovative methods;
4. Improving the assessment system, developing clear criteria for assessing competencies;
5. Encouraging students' project and research activities.

One of the problems identified during the research is teachers' insufficient knowledge and skills in applying the competency-based approach methodology. To solve this problem, it is proposed to improve the teacher training system and develop teaching aids and electronic resources in methodology.

Conclusions

Based on the research results, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. The competency-based approach in physics teaching helps to integrate students' fundamental knowledge with practical skills and develop their analytical thinking and problem-solving abilities.
2. A comprehensive approach is necessary for effectively forming and developing students' competencies in physics, which includes theoretical teaching, practical classes, laboratory work, project activities, and the use of modern technologies.
3. The developed modular methodology had a positive impact on increasing students' levels of all types of competencies (scientific-theoretical, practical-experimental, problem-solving creative, information-communicative, social-personal).
4. The effectiveness of implementing the competency-based approach in physics teaching largely depends on the teacher's professional preparation, skills in using modern pedagogical technologies, and the condition of the educational-material base.
5. Applying the STEM approach in teaching physics, strengthening interdisciplinary connections, and teaching based on real-life examples increase students' interest in the subject and develop their competencies.

Based on the research results, the following recommendations were developed for improving physics teaching in general education schools:

1. Improving curricula based on the competency-based approach, optimizing the volume of theoretical material, and increasing the share of practical activities;
2. Widely using modern information and communication technologies, virtual laboratories, and simulations in teaching physics;

3. Improving the teacher training system, organizing special courses on mastering the competency-based approach methodology;

4. Developing and implementing clear criteria for assessing competencies;

5. Encouraging students' project and research activities, organizing science olympiads, exhibitions, and competitions;

Studying international experience and adapting it to the national education system.

The research results can be used to improve physics teaching practices in general education schools, develop teacher training and professional development programs, and create educational-methodical literature.

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